

Correlation between Transcutaneous Bilirubin (TCB) and Total Serum Bilirubin (TSB) in Term Neonates Prior to Phototherapy: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract

Background: Accurate assessment of neonatal hyperbilirubinemia is crucial to prevent bilirubin-induced neurological dysfunction. Total serum bilirubin (TSB) estimation remains the diagnostic gold standard, while transcutaneous bilirubin (TCB) measurement provides a rapid, non-invasive alternative. This study aimed to evaluate the correlation between TCB and TSB values measured prior to initiation of phototherapy in term neonates.

Methods: This cross-sectional analysis included 100 term neonates enrolled in a randomized controlled trial conducted at a tertiary care hospital in Rajasthan. Prior to initiation of phototherapy, TCB was measured using a transcutaneous bilirubinometer, followed immediately by venous sampling for TSB estimation using an automated analyzer (Erba Mannheim XL-640/EM 360). Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation coefficient were used to assess the relationship between TCB and TSB values.

Results: The mean TCB level was 18.85 ± 1.90 mg/dL, while the mean TSB level was 18.87 ± 1.95 mg/dL, showing a negligible mean difference of 0.02 mg/dL. However, the Pearson correlation coefficient between TCB and TSB was $r = 0.35$, indicating a moderate positive correlation. Increasing variability between TCB and TSB measurements was observed at higher bilirubin levels (>18 mg/dL).

Conclusion: Although mean TCB values closely approximated mean TSB levels, the moderate correlation suggests that TCB alone is insufficient for precise individual-level clinical decision-making. TCB is a useful screening tool to identify neonates requiring further evaluation; however, confirmatory TSB estimation remains essential before initiating treatment, particularly at higher bilirubin levels.

Keywords: Neonatal Jaundice, Transcutaneous Bilirubin, Total Serum Bilirubin, Hyperbilirubinemia, Phototherapy, Correlation.

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Introduction

Neonatal hyperbilirubinemia affects approximately 60% of term infants during the first week of life and remains one of the most common causes of neonatal hospital admissions. While most cases are physiological, excessive unconjugated bilirubin may cross the immature blood-brain barrier and result in bilirubin-induced neurological dysfunction (BIND), including acute bilirubin encephalopathy and kernicterus [1].

Measurement of total serum bilirubin (TSB) through venous sampling is considered the gold standard for diagnosis and management decisions.

However, repeated blood sampling is invasive, painful, and resource-intensive. Transcutaneous bilirubin (TCB) measurement offers a rapid, non-invasive method that minimizes discomfort and reduces the need for repeated blood draws [2].

Previous studies have demonstrated good correlation between TCB and TSB, particularly at lower bilirubin levels. However, the accuracy of TCB may vary depending on bilirubin range, skin pigmentation, device characteristics, and local population factors [3]. Therefore, validation of TCB measurements in different clinical settings is

essential. This study aimed to assess the correlation between TCB and TSB levels prior to phototherapy in term neonates admitted to a tertiary care center in Rajasthan.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: A cross-sectional analysis was conducted among neonates enrolled in a randomized controlled trial at the Department of Pediatrics, Government Medical College & J.K. Lone Hospital, Kota, and Rajasthan.

Study Population: A total of 100 term neonates (gestational age 37–42 weeks) with clinically significant hyperbilirubinemia requiring phototherapy were included.

Inclusion Criteria

- Term neonates (37–42 weeks gestation)
- Postnatal age between 1 and 14 days
- Hyperbilirubinemia meeting American Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) 2004 phototherapy criteria

Exclusion Criteria

- Preterm (<37 weeks) or post-term (>42 weeks) neonates
- Major congenital anomalies
- Hemodynamic instability or requirement of ventilatory support

Measurement Procedure: TCB measurement was performed using a standard transcutaneous bilirubinometer over the sternum prior to initiation of phototherapy. Venous blood samples were collected immediately thereafter, and TSB was estimated using an automated analyzer (Erba Mannheim XL-640/EM 360).

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 22. Continuous variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation. Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was calculated to assess the relationship between TCB and TSB values. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Gender distribution of study participants (n = 100)

Gender	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Male	46	46
Female	54	54
Total	100	100

Table 2: Comparison of TcB and TSB Before Phototherapy

Statistics	TCB	TSB
No.	100	100
Mean	18.85	18.87
SD	1.9	1.95

Correlation Analysis: The Pearson correlation coefficient between TCB and TSB was $r = 0.35$, indicating a moderate positive correlation. Scatter plot analysis demonstrated increasing dispersion of

values at higher bilirubin levels (>17–18 mg/dL), suggesting reduced reliability of TCB measurements in this range.

Figure 1:

Discussion

The present study demonstrates that although mean TCB and TSB values measured prior to phototherapy are nearly identical, the correlation between individual measurements is only moderate ($r = 0.35$). This finding highlights the limitation of relying solely on TCB for individual clinical decision-making.

Several studies have reported stronger correlations between TCB and TSB. Kantroo et al. reported a correlation coefficient of 0.865, while Arunachalmath et al. and Tiwari et al. reported correlations exceeding 0.88 [3–5]. The comparatively lower correlation observed in the present study may be attributed to higher mean bilirubin levels, darker skin pigmentation, device-related variability, and environmental factors affecting optical measurements.

Previous literature suggests that the accuracy of transcutaneous bilirubinometry declines at higher bilirubin levels, which is consistent with the increasing variability observed in this study [6]. Therefore, while TCB serves as an effective screening tool, confirmatory serum bilirubin estimation remains essential when bilirubin levels approach treatment thresholds.

Conclusion

Transcutaneous bilirubin measurement demonstrated near-identical mean values compared with total serum bilirubin; however, only a moderate correlation was observed at the individual

level. TCB is a useful non-invasive screening tool that can reduce the need for blood sampling, but TSB estimation should remain the confirmatory diagnostic method, particularly in neonates with higher bilirubin levels or when treatment decisions are required.

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